

TOPDESIGN MODEL TOOLCHAIN

ABOUT TOPDESIGN: WHAT AND WHY

MERIDIONAL's **TopDesign** is a **tool chain integration platform** developed for multi-disciplinary analysis and optimisation (MDAO) in **wind energy**.

TopDesign supports researchers, engineers and practitioners in the wind energy sector who need to **simulate, design, operate, and investigate wind farms** (both conventional and airborne). They will benefit from **the capability to integrate existing and new models and workflows**.

This toolchain responds to three challenges:

- 1 The difficulty of adopting **different tools and models** when dealing with the analysis and design optimization of wind turbines and wind farms.
- 2 The **complexity of use** of existing MDAO platforms (e.g. DAKOTA and OpenMDAO)
- 3 The **lack of an integrated platform** specifically developed for the **wind energy** sector

WHAT TOPDESIGN CAN DO

It easily integrates and couples different models and tools in different formats and programming languages

It is easily extendible and adaptable by different users from both academia and industry

It is configurable and applicable to various kinds of MDAO tasks in the wind energy sector

TopDesign helps academia and industry **plan and design wind farms**, as it can also contribute to optimising to the wind farm layout. This **impacts on the energy yield** due to wake effects and thus influences the **cost of the wind farm**.

TopDesign platform:

<https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/TOPFARM/basic-plugins/topdesign>

PyP:

<https://pypi.org/project/top-design/>

THE PLATFORM: HOW IT'S MADE

TopDesign integrates three popular tools for wind farm modelling and design:

- **PyWake**: a wind farm simulation tool capable of computing flow fields, power production of individual turbines and the annual energy production (AEP) of a wind farm;
- **FLORIS**: a controls-focused wind farm simulation software incorporating steady-state engineering wake models into a performance-focused framework;
- **TopFarm**: a Python package that serves as a wind farm optimiser for both onshore and offshore wind farms.

METHODOLOGY: HOW IT WORKS

The platform is written with Python using an object-oriented programming methodology.

However, the different models and tools that need to be integrated or coupled through TopDesign don't have to be Python-based. They can:

Be written in different programming languages (e.g. Matlab, Fortran, C++)

Take different formats (like scripts, compiled executables)

Depending on the usage scenarios, these tools or models can also be open-source or commercial, in-house-developed or third-party-provided.

To enable smooth coupling and interaction, any existing custom tool/model is embedded or wrapped into a Python object representing the model.

Figure 1: A general Python model which embeds/wraps a custom model.

All relevant tools and models wrapped into different Python models can then be integrated or coupled into a system to carry out a multi-disciplinary analysis.

Figure 2: A system coupling multiple models with a directed graph defining the flow.

SOFTWARE DESIGN: WHAT YOU'LL FIND ON THE PLATFORM

The TopDesign platform is written as a Python package and contains:

Core components

Model and system classes,
utilities functions.

Wind farm simulation tools

Models for wind condition
and wind farm simulation.

Optimisers

Optimisation algorithms implemented
and integrated on the platform.

Examples

Working examples that demonstrate different
scenarios for using the platform.

USAGE GUIDE: HOW TO INSTALL TOP DESIGN

The TopDesign package can be easily installed from

PyPI using the command

```
pip install topdesign
```

GitLab, using the command:

```
pip install git+https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/TOPFARM/basic-plugins/topdesign.git
```

To clone and install TopDesign with developer options including minimal dependencies into the current active environment in an Anaconda Prompt, the commands are:

```
git clone https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/TOPFARM/basic-plugins/topdesign.git  
cd topdesign pip install-e
```

SUSTAINABILITY: HOW TOPDESIGN CAN BE USED BEYOND MERIDIONAL

The **TopDesign** platform ensures long-term sustainability through its open-source MIT licence, allowing anyone to use, modify, and redistribute the software while retaining the original licence and copyright notice.

This guarantees continued availability beyond the MERIDIONAL project for academic, personal, or commercial use. Its modular and flexible Python-based architecture enables integration with different tools and models, facilitating adoption and extension in various contexts.

Future developments may arise through new research projects or industrial collaborations, and additional funding would be beneficial for further development, maintenance, user support and training activities.

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